

Institute *of* **Physics**

**Environmental
Physics Group**

Newsletter

October 2001

EDITOR'S REPORT

The October newsletter contains several items of information that should be of interest to EPG members. Please note that the EPG has its own web page at <http://www.iop.org/IOP/Groups/EP/> which is regularly updated by Lucy Parkin.

The next meeting organised by the Group will be on Wednesday 31 October at IoP HQ on the subject of Environment and Sustainable Agriculture, a topic of great current economic, political, scientific and social importance. There is no charge for this half-day event, and travel bursaries are available to EPG members who wish to participate (contact Peter Hodgson for details). Please return the reply form to me if you wish to attend so that I can arrange sufficient catering.

Also included is a review of the book, *An Introduction to Environmental Physics: Planet Earth, Life and Climate* (by Nigel Mason, Peter Hughes and others), referred to on page 13 of the June newsletter.

May I remind you to continue to send me items for inclusion in future newsletters, preferably email attachments for easy editing.

Derek Rose

FORTHCOMING MEETINGS

Environment and Sustainable Agriculture

Wednesday 31 October, 13.30 – 17.00

Institute of Physics, 76 Portland Place, London

Organized by the Environmental Physics Group and the Environmental Chemistry Group of the Royal Society of Chemistry

Speakers:

Prof. P. Leeds-Harrison (Cranfield University): *Sustainable use of water in agriculture*

Dr. J.A. Garrett (Newcastle University): *Modelling and management of pesticide use in European horticulture*

Prof. P. Haygarth & Prof. D. Scholefield (IGER, North Wyke): *Sustainable use of fertilisers*

Prof. D. Fowler (CEH, Edinburgh): *Control of greenhouse gas emissions (e.g. NH₃, NO_x) from agriculture*

Note: there will be no charge for this meeting, but please let me know if you wish to attend so that adequate catering can be arranged. There is a tear-off reply coupon on the separate flyer.

Please also note that some travel bursaries will be available to enable EPG members (research students) to participate. Contact Peter Hodgson for details.

Dr. D.A. Rose, EPG Committee

OTHER NEWS AND INFORMATION

Climate of UK waters

A report issued by the Inter-Agency Committee on Marine Science and Technology (IACMST) describes the present (1999/2000) status and trends of climate, weather, nutrients, plankton, salinity, sea level, temperature and waves in UK waters. The report is available from the British Oceanographic Data Centre (email: ljr@bodc.ac.uk) or via the OceanNET web site (www.oceannet.org), which has been set up by the IACMST as a portal to data and information about the marine environment.

Graham Alcock

Energy technology technical brief

Following on from the technical brief on Nanotechnology, published in 2000, the Higher Education & Research Policy Department of the Institute is planning to produce a follow-up technical brief on low-emission technologies, particularly concentrating on renewable energy technologies and the contribution of fission and fusion based nuclear power.

The Department would like to receive ideas from Institute members concerning appropriate and relevant topics for inclusion in the technical brief.

Please forward ideas and comments to Tajinder Panesor at the Institute (e-mail: tajinder.panesor@iop.org).

T. Panesor

Energy and Resources in the 21st Century

Wednesday 7 November, 18.00 – 21.30

Lindop suite, Hatfield Campus, University of Hertfordshire.

Organized by EEESTA (East of England Engineering, Science and Technology Association)

This event will deal with key issues related to the global use of energy and sustainable resources in the 21st Century.

Keynote speakers

Ms Sara Parkin (Programme Director, Forum for the future), Dr. Malcolm Kennedy CBE FREng (Chairman, PB Power Ltd) and Mr. John Ingham (President-Elect of the Institute of Energy) who will Chair the meeting.

Programme:

18.00	Refreshments and Exhibition
18.45	Welcome and introductions
19.00	Sara Parkin
19.45	Dr. Malcolm Kennedy
20.30	Plenary
21.15	Closing remarks by Chairman
21.15	Vote of thanks
21.30	Close

THIS IS AN ALL TICKET EVENT, for tickets contact:

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Events Assistant
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The Future of Fusion Power

Wednesday 24 November, 18.30 – 20.00

Institute of Physics, 76 Portland Place, London

A lecture given by Derek Robinson, Head of Euratom/UKAEA Fusion Association at Culham Science Centre

BOOK REVIEW

Mason, Nigel & Hughes, Peter. *Introduction to Environmental Physics: Planet Earth, Life and Climate*. Taylor & Francis, London, 2001, xxiv + 463 pp., £80, ISBN 0-7484-0764-2 (hbk), £29,99, ISBN 0-7484-0765-0 (pbk)

The authors define environmental physics "as the response of living organisms to their environment within the framework of the physics of environmental processes and issues". This is to be compared with John Monteith's definition, given in his book *Principles of Environmental Physics*, as "the measurement and analysis of interactions between organisms and their physical environment", and to Egbert Boeker's and Rienk van Grondelle's definition, given in their book *Environmental Physics*, as "the physics concerning the identification and measurement of environmental problems". The present book recognises a broader field of environmental physics than these two very different books, attempting to bridge the gap between them, helped by contributions from Randall McMullan, Ross Reynolds, Lester Simmonds and John Twidell. It is aimed at the general reader and, in particular, post 16 year old students and first year undergraduates in science generally. It assumes the reader to have an understanding of basic physics and elementary algebra. Throughout the book there is a great deal of general discussion of issues, which is unexpected for a physics textbook

The book is arranged in twelve chapters. After the introductory chapter entitled "Environmental physics: processes and issues", the second chapter considers the human environment, relating the laws of thermodynamics to the energy exchanges of the human body. Chapters follow on the built environment, on the urban environment and on energy production, addressing the increasing concerns of pollution and the various options available to combat this. The next chapter on the use of remote sensing to observe the Earth's environment sets the scene for the following chapters that describe the transfer of solar energy through the Earth's atmosphere to the Earth's surface, weather and climate. This leads on to one chapter on physics and soils, and another on vegetation growth and the carbon balance. The final chapter considers environmental issues of the twenty-first century. Throughout the book there are short biographies of scientists that have made major contributions in the development of environmental physics. Worked examples and case studies are interspersed in the text, and all the chapters (except the first and last) give a set of discussion and quantitative questions that will be useful to students to consolidate their understanding of the subject. Appendices provide additional physics and derivations of some of the formulae quoted in the text, an explanation of the synoptic weather chart, environmental risk and environmental impact assessment of ozone-related disasters, a list of units and constants, and the answers to the numerical questions. The book ends with a Bibliography and a useful Glossary.

The chapters in this multi-authored book vary in the breadth of coverage of subject matter and the depth of physics employed in explanations. Perhaps the best chapters are those on the weather and climate. Other chapters are less comprehensive, sometimes concentrating on issues rather than the physics. Environmental physics is a subject that is

concerned with processes observed in everyday life and thus is an excellent means of teaching basic physics. With this in mind, much more could have been written on some of the topics, for example on the physics of noise and light pollution, and on atmospheric optics with explanations of the haloes observed around the sun and moon.

The authors have attempted with fair success to provide an introduction into the many facets of environmental physics. However, environmental physics is a very broad subject so that, in this initial venture, it would be unrealistic to expect coverage of every facet. In any future edition, the authors should consider including a chapter on the ocean environment, together with discussions on soil salinity, on soil erosion through the transport of material by wind and water, on waste disposal and on groundwater pollution. An account of the soil-plant-atmosphere continuum needs a discussion on the soil-root interface that is absent in the chapters on soil and vegetation. An oversight in the present book has been the omission of an account of diffusion that occurs in many environmental situations.

In spite of the above shortcomings, this book offers a good introduction to the wide range of issues and their interdependency with which environmental physics is concerned. The authors have succeeded in producing a much more comprehensive account of the subject than is contained in other books with a similar title. It will be useful to students and others in providing an outline of the physics involved, although generally they will have to look elsewhere for in-depth explanations.

E.G. Youngs

PROFILE OF THE EPG COMMITTEE

Chair, Prof. Edward Youngs graduated in physics at Kings College, London, in 1953, and obtained his PhD in soil physics at Cambridge in 1956. He joined the Agricultural Research Council Unit of Soil Physics, Cambridge, in 1955, transferring to Rothamsted Experimental Station in 1977. He did research on the physics of soil-water movement and on its applications in agriculture and hydrology, for which he was awarded the degree of ScD in 1972. Now, in retirement, he continues research and consultancy work as a Visiting Professor at Cranfield University at Silsoe. He has been on the Editorial Boards of several scientific journals and is currently an Associate Editor of the *European Journal of Soil Science*.

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Vice-chair, Dr. Alastair McCartney graduated in physics from the University of Strathclyde and obtained a PhD in environmental physics from Nottingham University in 1975. At Nottingham and then at Brighton Polytechnic he worked on solar radiation before moving to Lancaster University to work on air pollution dispersal. He has been at the Institute of Arable Crops Research, Rothamsted since 1978 where he works on the interaction between environmental factors and crop pathogens. He is interested in the application of physics to the understanding of biological systems. Since 1990 he has been the leader of the Oilseeds Pathology Group in the Plant Pathology Department.

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Honorary Secretary and treasurer, Dr. Peter Hodgson graduated in physics and applied physics from the University of Nottingham in 1986. After a spell at BT Laboratories he studied for an MSc and then PhD in optical physics at Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh. His PhD, awarded in 1994, was concerned with developing a spectroscopic technique for the detection of oil pollution in water. From there he took a post at the NERC Institute of Hydrology, where his role included the development and application of instruments for measuring water quality, soil moisture and transpiration processes. Since 1997 he has been employed as a Project Manager at Bristol Industrial and Research Associates Limited, where his dominant interest is in optical instruments for the characterisation of aerosol particles.

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WWW editor, Miss Lucy Parkin graduated from UMIST with a BSc in Physics with Environmental Science in 1998 she then went on to complete an MSc in Environmental Technology at Imperial College, London. There she completed a dissertation on the effects of air pollution on visibility in London. She now works as a consultant in the Air Quality department of WVS Atkins Environment

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Newsletter editor, Dr. Derek Rose, CPhys, FInstP was born in 1937 and educated at Devizes Grammar School and UCL (BSc 1958). He obtained PhD in Soil Physics from London University in 1962. Subsequent career in agricultural physics and biomathematics at Rothamsted Experimental Station, CSIRO Division of Land Research, and Glasshouse Crops Research Institute. Since 1985, Lecturer in Soil-Plant Relations in Department of Agricultural & Environmental Science, University of Newcastle upon Tyne. Sometime editor of the *European Journal of Soil Science*, the leader in its field.

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Dr. Karen Aplin graduated with a degree in Applied Physics and Philosophy from the University of Durham in 1997. She then did a PhD in the Department of Meteorology, University of Reading, awarded in 2000, where she developed an instrument to measure the electrical properties of atmospheric ions. From 2000-2001 she worked in the Atmospheric Sciences Research Group, University of Hertfordshire on an EU urban pollution project and independently pursued her research into atmospheric ions and aerosol. She has recently joined the Space Science and Technology Department, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, to extend her research area beyond the Earth's atmosphere.

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Dr. Ian Colbeck graduated from Queen Mary College, moved to Oxford for his Masters and then to Lancaster for his PhD. After working at the British Antarctic Survey he moved to the University of Essex in 1984 where he now heads the aerosol science group. His research interests include the physical and chemical properties of aerosols, environment/society interactions, processing of nanoparticle materials and urban air quality. He has published nearly 200 articles in refereed journals, conference proceedings and books. He is a Fellow of the Institute of Physics and is currently President of the Aerosol Society. Click here for further personal details

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Dr. John Garland joined the nuclear research establishment at Harwell immediately after graduating in physics at Bristol University in 1960. He worked for a while at other nuclear establishments before returning to Harwell to join the Aerosol Group. He carried out research on the dispersion of nuclear and non-nuclear pollutants and their deposition to crops and other surfaces. The pollutants of interest included radioiodine, tritium and tritiated water, sulphur dioxide, ozone and particulate substances. He also investigated the resuspension of deposited radionuclides and the transfer of radioactivity from the sea to land in sea spray, and examined the size distribution of water droplets in fog and the effects of air pollution on visibility in fog and haze.

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Mr. Peter Hughes studied physics and chemistry at Liverpool University and followed a teaching career in physics, mathematics and statistics in the secondary, further, higher and tertiary education sectors. While teaching he took part-time MPhil and MEd degrees from the universities of Bristol and Hull. He is currently Lecturer in Physics and Mathematics at Kingsway College, London and has taught courses on Science Education at the Polytechnic of North London and mathematics for Science Undergraduates at Birkbeck College. He is Chair of the Environmental Physics Group's Education Subcommittee, which is committed to raising the profile of Environmental Physics at all levels and initiating educational change in that area. He is Honorary Visiting Lecturer, School of Engineering, City University. Email: phughes@kingsway.ac.uk

Ms. Sheila Morris graduated in Physics with Medial Physics from the University of Bristol in 2000. During her final year she investigated the effect of static electric fields on the deposition of bacteriological and radioactive aerosols. She is now doing a PhD, involving the study of plant cell walls using the Atomic Force Microscope.

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Dr. Douglas Peirson studied physics at the University of Exeter, and worked at the Royal Aircraft Establishment before joining UKAEA, Harwell in 1947. He continued working there and retired as Branch Head in the Environmental and Medical Sciences Division in 1986 but worked part time until 1989. He was awarded a DSc from London University in 1970. He has published widely in the field of Environmental Sciences, particularly on radioactivity as a tracer of environmental processes. Apart from other findings, these studies demonstrated the interdependence of the compartments of the environment – the atmosphere, geosphere, hydrosphere and the biosphere.
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Ms. Alexandra Wilson Having obtained Physics Degree BSc (Hons), she then worked on an MSc entitled "Energy Conservation and the Environment". Subsequently she joined Ove Arup & Partners in 1992 and dealt with problems related to the design and analysis of the internal environment of buildings. She works as a member of the Mechanical, Electrical and Public Health Engineering (MEP) Team in Research and Development. She has a strong interest in the area of energy efficiency in buildings.

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